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UTILITY OF SOUL SOFTWARE FOR LIBRARY AUTOMATION

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Process and Challenges to Automated Library in India

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(Abstract: This paper discussed the Process & challenges to Automated Library in India in some different point of views as like technological, economical and attitudinal challenges. Technological process which include both the hardware and the software of library automation. Economical aspect faced each and every library in all over the world. The initial cost of establishing a computer system is beyond the reach of most organizations and institutions. The last aspect is discussed is attitudinal problem, in this approach the common thing is that among librarians there are two groups often give insufficient thought to the real value of the computer to the organization/institution and make uneconomical, haphazard use of the facility. Here in this article mentioned some recommended improvements for betterment of the automation in library and information field).

(Keywords: Computer Hardware & Software, Library Automation, Networking, Internet, Digital & Electronic Resources and ICT).

Introduction

Modern society is characterized by an increasing need for specialized institutions in various fields of activity for the performance of their day-to-day functions as well as research and consultancy work. These institutions require speedy access to qualitative published information. Exposure, the methods of storage and dissemination of information are changing fast, so no library can store all published information and can provide efficient services with its old manual operations. (Alabi GA 1984). Therefore, "Automation" is important and necessary to handle the vast amount of information and for providing faster, accurate, precise, efficient, and effective information and services as well.

The emergence of information communication technologies (ICT) have revolutionized access to information for the business world, education, intellectual development, recreational and sport as well as social development. Information communication devices to include e-mail, world wide web (WWW), file transfer protocol (FTP), urnet and telnet. Libraries all over the world have benefited tremendously with ICT initiatives and applications thus changing the traditional ways of library operations. These ICT initiatives are made possible through digital technology. According to Kennedy and Davis (2006) digital technology is of importance when information is to be gathered, store, retrieved and evaluated. In order to bridge the gap between traditional and modern methods of information storage, retrieval and provision in digital age that the use of ICT in library operations must be seriously emphasized.

Technological Aspects

Need of computers is present in all areas depending upon its usage. They range from acquisition control, serial control, and cataloguing and circulation control. They are also used for library manager's evaluation of reports, statistics, etc. For the good administration of the library computers are used in all levels of work. Above all, the unique characteristics of computer made it the right choice for the library world.

Computers right from the beginning are considered to aid man, in doing various operations.

Technological problems include both the hardware, i.e., the computer as an instrument for information processing and the software, i.e. the methodology which is applied. The major problems faced today in terms of the hardware are due to the variety of computers being used in different types of research and business institutions. The computers, manufactured by various firm are not compatible.

Information retrieval work requires machines more sophisticated than those manufactured indigenously and few imported machines are capable of handling information retrieval applications. The random access facility and disks large enough for storage of bibliographic information are not readily available. In most institutions, organizational goal receive priority over the library's requirements, meaning that the librarian must use the computer available rather than what is actually required according to specifications. Library activities in all institutions are done through sharing disk space as well as computer time. Therefore, when the storage capacity is not large enough to accommodate various types of data, bibliographic data are given the lowest priority. On-line facilities are rare in India.

Economic Aspects

The major obstacle for any innovations in developing countries is the lack of resources. The initial cost of establishing a computer system is beyond the reach of most organizations and institutions. Library and information processing is done either with spare computer capacity made available by the institution itself, or with computer time hired from another institution. The cost of hiring computer time and storage space is very high and often cannot be justified at the management level by cost-benefit analysis. At IIT, for example, CPU time per hour cost ₹ 1000 for educational purposes and ₹ 2000 for business and industrial use. Moreover, the computer provides only paper printout, and the paper often cost more than the processing. Few developing countries can afford the machine-readable databases, either. The tapes are very

expensive and because foreign exchange is involved in subscribing to them, it is even more difficult for most organizations in India and other developing countries to afford them. The annual subscription rate of one database is now approximately \$ 8000. Library tasks often overlap and their peculiar nature seldom makes the advantages of computerization seem very convincing in the light of cost benefit analysis.

In India, libraries and information centers are attached to government organizations or research institutions, so library services cannot be calculated on a profit/loss basis. Long term benefits have to keep in mind while justifying such services. The libraries that have computerized some of their services or operations often have not taken such steps as a result of serious thought. Computerization has glamour of its own in the minds of many librarians. Overly enthusiastic librarians often run uneconomical programmes, producing lengthy listings for instance in the name of computerized service. Often the manual method is used concurrently with the computerized system because of a lack of faith on the part of staff and users. The duplication of work and the cost involved in these cases is obviously unjustifiable; the librarian should know which aspects of service should be mechanized. An example of an economically visible computerized library activity is the centralized acquisitions but also eliminates the cost of duplicate purchasing.

Attitudinal Aspects

Computers appear very awesome to developing countries. They are powerful machines which can perform many functions and therefore offer a solution to the many types of manual inefficiency which often plague the developing countries. Among librarians there are two groups often give insufficient thought to the real value of the computer to the organization/institution and make uneconomical, haphazard use of the facility. The other group, still the majority in developing countries, lacks knowledge of the potential and consequences of library automation. There is constant tension between this traditional librarian group and the 'new wave' librarians. Professionals of the majority group do not realize that computers cannot replace human intelligence. Due to the accuracy essential for data input in library services, the librarian/information scientist is indispensable. The National Library of Calcutta conducted an experiment to computerize the Indian National Bibliography in 1968.

The scheme failed, however, because labour unions opposed it fearing retrenchment of library staff. Among developing countries, the attitudes of India's librarians are typical. They are not confident about automated services. Library staff should therefore be trained in programming and thus be made aware of the work involved in automation. They will then realize that automation will not take away their jobs. They will also realize that computers are machines which have their limitations as well as their advantages. The communication gap between the librarian and the computer specialist is another major hindrance in establishing any

effective automated system in a library. There is often disagreement among the librarian, the programmer and the systems analyst. Librarians should be trained in computer programming and computer specialists should be versed in the special needs of library automation. Only then can a common language evolve among the three and projects are started. Administrative personnel assume a very important role in decision making. Their enthusiasm, support and conviction can help realize any new plan, just as their apathy and lack of understanding of the need for accurate and speedy information can jeopardize any effort. Although many things have taken a favourable turn in India, the majorities of those at the management level unfortunately are not conversant with the development of information science and are unaware of the important role of information in all areas of national development. This very often results in insufficient planning, which in turn curbs the enthusiasm of imaginative information scientists and librarians. Due to this lack of appreciation, priorities are poorly ordered and funds are not well allocated. Administrators also have a tendency to underestimate or overestimate the capacity of automation. Any information system or service is planned for the best possible benefit to its users. Unless the users are mentally prepared to accept a new system, however, it cannot be effective. Indian users are still unfamiliar and overawed by computers, so computer awareness and interest has to be fostered to enable proper utilization of a system.

Conclusion

With advancement of technology the library automation are moving towards digital resources, with are found to be less expensive and more helpful for easy access. These are helpful especially to distant learners who have limited time to access the libraries from outside by the commonly available electronic resources mainly CD ROMs, OPACs and Internet etc., which are replacing the print media. Digital and electronic resources have played a vital role in all fields of human life. Without knowing these technologies, we cannot access them. Now users, librarians and higher authorities related to particular organization have greater responsibility to give the effective accurate, reliable, skill full automation to the libraries. Library automation is very important for research and development.

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Dr. Pradeep Kumar Trivedi obtained his M.Sc Mathematics in 1989, M.Lib.I.Sc in 1991 and Ph.D in Library & Information Science From Dr. H.S. Gour V.V. Sagar in 2005. He also got the Degree of LLB in 2009 from R.D.V.V Jabalpur and M.Sc Computer Science in 2014 from M.L.C.N.U. Bhopal. He has 20 year experience of College Librarian in addition to 3 year experience of Junior Scientific Assistant in Indian Largest Defence Organization “ Defence Scientific Information and Documentation Centre” (DESIDOC), New Delhi. He contributed more than 20 research papers in various Journals, national and international conferences.

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